

Philippine College of Criminology Graduate School

An Analysis on the Effect of Transitioning of Administration on Drug-Related Crime Rates of Gandara Community Precinct

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ABSTRACT

A change in the PNP Chief affects the whole organization; a change in the Chief of Police in a station also affects those in the line; and a change in the presidential administration will have an impact not only on policing but also on governance as a whole. Both internationally and locally, illegal drugs are still far from being eradicated. In the Philippines, the fight against drugs was prioritized during the Duterte administration. This study aims to lay down the effects of the transition of administration from the “Duterte” administration to the “Marcos” administration on drug-related crime rates in the Gandara Police Community Precinct. Through interviews and surveys, this study shows whether there is still continuity with the operational plans in the fight against drug-related crimes. Results showed that there was no significant effect of the transition on drug-related crime rates in the transition period. However, after more than a year since the transition, a significant change has been observed. This study was limited within the one-year transition due to time constraints. Of the recommendations in this research, a longer period for the study is highly recommended for a more accurate result.

It can be concluded that, the results and discussions regarding the perceived effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct demonstrate a generally positive impact on various aspects of law enforcement and community engagement. The findings reveal that drug awareness drives have been highly effective, with increased community participation and engagement, as Participants 1 and 2 noted. This positive response underscores the success of efforts to raise awareness about drug abuse and foster community involvement in addressing this issue.

The researcher recommend, that the Gandara Police Community Precinct prioritize drug awareness campaigns, community engagement, intelligence-led law enforcement strategies, and initiatives to boost police morale. Efforts should be made to address any identified areas for improvement, such as enhancing communication strategies and ensuring consistent community involvement in decision-making processes. Maintaining a proactive and collaborative approach will be essential for sustaining the positive outcomes observed during administrative transitions and effectively addressing drug-related challenges within the community.

Keywords: *Transitioning of Administrations, Gandara Police Community Precinct, Drug- Related Crimes, Duterte Administration, Marcos Administration.*

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. *Background of Study*

Both internationally and locally, illegal drugs are still far from being eradicated. In the Philippines, the fight against drugs was prioritized during the Duterte administration. There have been many studies assessing the effectiveness of the Drug War of the Duterte Administration, and some proved that it was effective, yet there were allegations of human rights violations. Crime rates have significantly dropped since the previous administration initiated the drug war, which can probably imply the effectiveness of the drug war. After a year in office under the new president, assessing whether there is continuity in implementing the operations against drugs is timely.

I chose this topic because I was once part of the Station Drug Enforcement Unit in Marikina, which highlighted my career. I will be in the service for ten years in September 2024. I have been assigned to Station Drug Enforcement Unit Marikina from 2015–2019 and have been awarded the NCRPO Drug Buster Award for 2017–2018. Due to that accomplishment, our station was awarded the Best Station Drug Enforcement Unit in 2019. I have witnessed and experienced first-hand the efficiency and effectiveness of the operation plan for the war on drugs. There was a significant decrease in crimes.

I am currently assigned as a bike patroller at Gandara Police Community Precinct, Mesic Police Station 11, Manila Police District. Through this study, the researcher seeks to learn about the effects of the transition of administration.

As a personal experience, a change in the PNP chief affects the whole organization. A change in the Chief of Police at a station also affects those in the line. After the war on drugs, we moved to a new era under the Marcos administration. This research aims to learn about the effects of the transition of the administration from the Duterte administration to the Marcos administration.

➤ *International Background*

Since the implementation of US President Richard Nixon's anti-drug campaign in 1971, which involved the transfer of responsibility for regulating illegal narcotics to law enforcement agencies, there has been a notable increase in illicit drug consumption, the growth of international drug syndicates, and a rise in civilian fatalities. The implementation of Nixon's anti-drug policies resulted in the criminalization and public stigmatization of individuals engaged in illicit drug consumption. This approach led to a significant increase in the number of individuals incarcerated, as indicated by global data, which suggests that approximately 20% of detainees were apprehended for drug-related offenses. It is worth noting that a considerable portion of these individuals were merely in possession of drugs for personal use (International Drug Policy Consortium 2018). However, despite the growing allocation of resources towards enforcement-driven strategies to reduce the supply of drugs and disrupt the global drug trade, there has been a general decrease in illegal drug prices due to abundant supply and an increase in drug purity since 1990. This trend implies that the expansion of law enforcement efforts to control the global illegal drug market is proving to be ineffective. The growing attitude of disappointment regarding the criminalization of drug usage has garnered increasing attention in recent years. This sentiment has been particularly articulated by Helen Clark, the former Prime Minister of New Zealand, who is well recognized as a prominent figure in the global campaign against illicit drugs.

The present perception of inadequacy prompts an inquiry into the specific ideal from which contemporary global and national drug policy diverges. If the societal struggle against illicit substances is conceptualized as a conflict, how is the achievement of success in this conflict defined and established? If we consider violence and peace as opposing concepts, the question arises as to how peace can be achieved in a society that is plagued by the prevalence of illicit drug usage. To address the issue of drug abuse, government officials and influential individuals employ politically attractive ideas to rally backing and allocate resources toward heightened state intervention against drug syndicates. The concept of peace is frequently utilized as a prominent linguistic device in the discourse around the fight against illegal drugs.

➤ *National Background*

Upon assuming office on June 30, 2016, President Rodrigo R. Duterte of the Philippines initiated an unparalleled endeavor aimed at combating the use of illegal drugs. The individual committed to addressing the use of illegal drug activity within the nation, asserting that it was causing significant harm to numerous Filipino households and undermining the prospects of the younger generation. He proclaimed a comprehensive campaign against illegal substances, encompassing individuals engaged in drug consumption, distribution, production, and provision. Furthermore, the individual urged the Philippine criminal justice system to effectively combat the pervasive issue of drug-related activities.

Moreover, alongside these potential positive outcomes, numerous reports and international organizations have raised concerns about human rights violations during the drug war. Allegations of extrajudicial killings, arbitrary arrests, and other abuses have sparked widespread criticism. It is crucial to consider both the positive outcomes and the negative consequences when evaluating the overall impact of the drug war.

Considering these considerations, conducting comprehensive and unbiased research is essential to providing a nuanced understanding of the situation. This research should consider various perspectives, analyze data critically, and address both the perceived benefits and the alleged human rights violations associated with the drug war. This holistic approach will contribute to a more informed and balanced assessment of the necessity and effectiveness of such policies.

In discussing the effectiveness of the drug war during the past administration, PNP data has been used to argue that crime rates, particularly drug-related crimes, have significantly decreased since the initiation of the campaign. This data might show a correlation between the drug war and reduced crime rates.

Meanwhile, based on the official records of the Dangerous Drugs Board (DDB), the governmental body entrusted with the formulation of laws about illicit substances within the Philippines, the estimated number of present drug users in the country amounts to approximately 1.8 million individuals. Furthermore, a substantial population of approximately 4.8 million Filipino citizens has acknowledged engaging in the use of illegal drugs on at least one occasion throughout their lifetimes. Most drug users, specifically 91%, are adults, with men comprising 87% of this population. Additionally, approximately 80% of drug users have attained a high school education. A majority of individuals, specifically 67%, are currently engaged in employment. In the Philippines, the prevailing substance of abuse is a derivative of methamphetamine known as shabu, sometimes referred to as the "poor man's cocaine." Based on research published by the United Nations in 2012, it was found that the Philippines exhibited the highest prevalence of methamphetamine misuse in comparison to other nations in the East Asian region. Specifically, approximately 2.2% of individuals aged 16 to 64 years in the Philippines were identified as users of methamphetamines.

➤ *Local Background*

Gandara is within the heart of Manila's Chinatown in Binondo, next to San Nicolas. It is composed of 15 barangays, namely: barangays 288, 290, 291, 294, 295, 296, 297, 298, 299, 300, 301, 302, 303, 304, and 305 and within the territory of Gandara Community Precinct.

Since 2022, MPD-Meisic Station 11 has had three chiefs of police. While Gandara Police Station had three commanders for the last three years, with the changes in leadership came changes in duty hours, rules, holiday duties, and regulations.

B. Related Literature

➤ *Foreign Literature*

In recent times, the issue of drug abuse and drug addiction has emerged as a significant societal concern. To meet the societal demand for drug misuse prevention, law enforcement agencies around the world allocate substantial resources to enhance the magnitude and efficacy of their interventions. Nevertheless, due to the swift transformations in societal dynamics, individuals involved in drug-related criminal activities are also endeavoring to elude investigations by engaging in the production, transportation, and distribution of illicit substances across many geographical areas. Consequently, this poses a considerable challenge to the effective implementation of drug prevention measures. In contrast to other prominent criminal offenses, the utilization of illicit drugs exhibits an elevated propensity for sustained engagement in other unlawful pursuits, including acts of aggression, fraudulent behavior, and theft. Furthermore, drug offenders typically exhibit a lack of proactive engagement with law enforcement regarding their criminal activities, thereby potentially leading to a significant underestimation of the true extent of the drug problem. Significantly, the burgeoning body of evidence in recent years indicates a strong association between drug-related criminal activities and acts of terrorism. Hence, the primary objective for law enforcement agencies is to formulate effective tactics to address this matter (Tsai et al., 2019).

The high percentage of recidivism represents a significant challenge in addressing drug-related offenses. Individuals who have been convicted of drug-related offenses exhibit a greater propensity for recidivism after their release from incarceration. The high percentage of recidivism undermines the efficacy of law enforcement interventions and contributes to significant socioeconomic issues. The primary factors contributing to the recurrence of drug-related criminal behavior are financial gain and social associations. Given the intricate nature of the drug trade, substantial profits can be generated through the interplay of transactions between the upstream and downstream sectors. Motivated by the prospect of financial gain, drug distributors are willing to assume the inherent risk of recidivism, ensuring a steady stream of cash. Another significant source of income stems from individuals with substance dependence. Drug distributors are consistently motivated to make revenue by actively recruiting new individuals who become addicted to drugs and then growing their dependency on these substances. Peer relationships are frequently utilized to exert an influence on the cognitive processes of individuals struggling with substance addiction, compelling them to engage in criminal actions within the group because of peer pressure or a need for social acceptance (Esiri, 2016). Consequently, peer interactions have the potential to induce relapse into criminal conduct among those struggling with addiction while also exhibiting a significant influence on the prevalence of illicit drug consumption. The recidivism of drug crimes can be attributed to two primary factors, both of which are associated with the connections among those involved. To address this issue, law enforcement agencies should implement a community-based approach that aims to uncover the underlying perceptions of criminal conduct and effectively mitigate the recurrence of drug-related offenses (Hughes et al., 2017).

In other forms of discussion, it can be noted that individuals possess the ability to engage with diverse sources and contexts of interaction, enabling them to access, appropriate, and negotiate discourses about tokhang. Through this process, individuals can construct their moral stances. The study conducted by Warburg and Jensen (2020) on ethnography in urban poor areas, as well as the analyses of Facebook comments by Camacho and Montiel (2021), Hapal (2019), and Uyheng and Montiel (2021), provide evidence of the widespread acceptance of institutional messages. These messages, particularly state discourses emphasizing the importance of punishing drug personalities for the purpose of community security, have gained significant popularity. The killings could potentially be portrayed as a moral method for attaining retributive and divine justice to justify the implementation of tokhang. This justification is further reinforced by portraying opponents, such as the political opposition and mainstream media, as being corrupt (Montiel, 2021). While discussions around social justice, the well-being of families and neighbors, and religious beliefs can be pertinent and employed as arguments against the implementation of tokhang, they are often considered secondary to the overarching concern of community safety (Warburg & Jensen, 2020). The utilization of discourses about human rights exhibited a lack of consistency, which can be attributed to the portrayal of individuals involved in drug-related activities as being devoid of human qualities (Hapal, 2019; Warburg & Jensen, 2020). Nevertheless, the constrained utilization of human rights discourses may also stem from sociolinguistic disparities. A study conducted by Uyheng and Montiel (2021) examined Facebook comments and found that discussions pertaining to community security, irrespective of one's stance on the policy, were predominantly conveyed in Filipino. On the other hand, conversations concerning democratic integrity were predominantly conducted in English. The observed variations in language usage within a society where language and social class are closely linked serve as evidence of how one's social status and the circumstances of social interactions influence the accessibility and significance of specific discourses.

With the high demand to maintain or continuously lessen the crime rate, it is also important to keep our officers motivated. Factor analysis revealed five broad primary motivational factors that motivate police in their work, which are: 1) feeling valued; 2) achievement; 3) workplace relationships; 4) the work itself; and 5) pay (Sommerfeldt, 2010). The police organization, regardless of modernization, is still human-oriented. The police managers need to keep in mind and ensure methods for motivating officers and men working under them (Gupta, 2002). Based on studies, motivation levels drop dramatically during the first two years of an officer's service and generally do not improve until nearing compulsory retirement (Sommerfeldt, 2010).

➤ *Local Literature*

President Duterte has placed significant emphasis on the war on drugs as a key component of his policy agenda. The primary subject of this study is "Project Tokhang," which is the focus due to its controversial nature. "Project Tokhang" is officially defined in the memorandum circular of the Philippine National Police (PNP, 2016) as the implementation of door-to-door visits to convince individuals suspected of engaging in illegal drug-related activities to cease their involvement. The circular provides a rationale for this action by highlighting the prevalence of the drug problem among the underprivileged and impoverished segments of society. It suggests that the government's attention has been primarily directed towards apprehending high-level drug traffickers, thereby neglecting the deteriorating drug situation at the grassroots level. The recognized source of harm is attributed to the escalating issue of drug abuse. The text employs pleasant language to depict its operations, yet subtly implies the utilization of force using euphemistic phrases like the neutralization of illegal drug personalities. The communication conveyed by President Duterte has a heightened degree of explicitness in its promotion of violent actions. In the context of addressing a police audience, the speaker emphasized the importance of adhering to their responsibilities and refraining from engaging in deceitful behavior. Furthermore, the speaker expressed a willingness to make the ultimate sacrifice in service of the police force. "If you fulfill your obligation and inadvertently cause the demise of 1,000 individuals while carrying out that duty, I shall offer you protection." According to Francisco (2016). In a broader sense, the orations delivered by the individual in question portray the acts of violence as morally justifiable, asserting that they are integral to fulfilling his obligations and responsibilities as a leader who is committed to maintaining the pledges made during his campaign. The author additionally portrays drug users as dehumanized and deserving of negative treatment. This is evident in their characterization of drug users as individuals with diminished cognitive capacity due to drug use, rendering them incapable of rehabilitation (Camacho & Montiel, 2021). Furthermore, the author employs war metaphors to depict drug users and dealers as adversaries who pose a threat to society, thereby justifying their exclusion or even eradication (Brasilino, 2019).

The wording employed in the official police circular and the vocal statements made by the president have been subject to criticism by the United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights because of their perceived endorsement of the utilization of deadly force. The administration's discourses were challenged by several organizations, including human rights, legal, and health groups, who emphasized the importance of upholding human rights and approaching the drug problem as a matter of public health (Geronimo, 2017). According to PhilRights (2021) and other human rights organizations, there is evidence to suggest that those living in poverty are disproportionately subjected to tokhang, resulting in harmful consequences for the families of those who have been slain because of the drug war. The criticisms have also been reiterated by the Catholic Church and academic establishments (Curato, 2017), with the Church using arguments about the sacredness of life in their pronouncements opposing tokhang (Valles, 2018).

The mainstream media has extensively covered the discourse emanating from both the administration and its adversaries. The inclusion of news stories about instances of drug-related homicides has bolstered official discourses through the prioritization of state sources and the utilization of ostensibly impartial event-driven reporting, granting the government the authority to manipulate

the narrative (Soriano, David, & Atun, 2021). One of the prevailing narratives highlighted in these news broadcasts is the concept of nanlaban, which presents instances of killings as acts of self-defense by the police due to alleged resistance from the "suspects" (Lamchek, 2017). The media extensively reported on incidents involving masked vigilantes, often characterizing the individuals killed by these vigilantes as victims while referring to those who died in contact with the police as suspects. Drawing predominantly from law enforcement sources, the reports enhance the availability of governmental narratives that propagate apprehension surrounding illicit drug consumption and criminal activity while simultaneously dehumanizing those who have fallen victim to the tokhang campaign (Soriano et al., 2021). In addition to traditional media outlets, social media platforms have emerged as a significant arena for the dissemination, alteration, and negotiation of diverse institutional discourses. Nevertheless, the convergence of social media algorithms, the employment of individuals specifically tasked with spreading discord (referred to as hired trolls), and the emotionally charged nature of news about the drug war (Ong & Cabañes, 2018) can amplify certain messages and render them more readily available, contingent upon an individual's personal history, social milieu, and psychological attributes.

In addition to the influence of social context on the accessibility of specific discourses, variations in support for the war on drugs can also be attributed to individual-level cognitive factors, such as the personal endorsement of the president and the perceived connection between drugs and crime (Labor & Gastardo-Conaco, 2017). Furthermore, moral foundations, right-wing authoritarianism, and threat perception have been identified as additional cognitive factors that contribute to differing levels of support for the war on drugs (Nerona, 2017). Moreover, affective factors, including feelings of hatred and compassion, have also been found to play a role in shaping individuals' stances on the war on drugs (Labor & Gastardo-Conaco, 2017).

➤ *Synthesis of Related Literature*

The literature on the drug war in the Philippines reveals a complex interplay of factors and perspectives. Foreign literature emphasizes the global challenge of drug-related criminal activities, linking them to terrorism and emphasizing the need for effective tactics to address the issue (Tsai et al., 2019). Recidivism in drug crimes is highlighted, with financial gain and social associations identified as significant contributors (Esiri, 2016). Community-based approaches are suggested to address underlying perceptions and mitigate recurrences (Hughes et al., 2017). On the local front, "Project Tokhang" is at the center of President Duterte's drug war, characterized by door-to-door visits to curb illegal drug activities (PNP, 2016). The language used by Duterte and official police communications has faced criticism for endorsing violence, dehumanizing drug users, and justifying deadly force (Francisco, 2016; Camacho & Montiel, 2021). Human rights organizations, the Catholic Church, and academic institutions have raised concerns about the disproportionate impact on the poor and the violation of human rights (PhilRights, 2021; Curato, 2017). The media plays a crucial role, with narratives of self-defense (nanlaban) shaping public perception and social media influencing discourse through algorithms and hired trolls (Soriano et al., 2021; Ong & Cabañes, 2018). Individual-level cognitive factors, including the endorsement of the president and perceptions of the connection between drugs and crime, as well as affective factors like feelings of hatred and compassion, contribute to varying levels of support for the drug war (Labor & Gastardo-Conaco, 2017; Nerona, 2017). The synthesis underscores the need for a comprehensive and nuanced examination of the drug war, considering its global context, local implementation, societal implications, and the diverse perspectives shaping public opinion.

C. *Related Studies*

➤ *Foreign Studies*

According to Chakravarthy et al. (2013), the persistent misuse of illicit substances remains a significant global health concern. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), in 2010, almost 5 percent of the global population engaged in the use of illicit substances. Furthermore, it is estimated that roughly 27 million individuals, which accounts for 0.6 percent of the adult population worldwide, might be categorized as individuals facing challenges associated with drug dependency. According to estimates, the misuse of alcohol leads to approximately 2.5 million fatalities annually, while the consumption of substances such as heroin, cocaine, and other illicit narcotics is responsible for approximately 0.1 to 0.2 million deaths per year. Substance misuse, apart from its lethal consequences, also gives rise to substantial morbidity, hence imposing a considerable societal burden through the management of drug addiction. According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the global expenses associated with addressing drug misuse are expected to range from \$200 to \$250 billion, equivalent to around 0.3 to 0.4 percent of the global gross domestic product (GDP). Furthermore, it has been estimated that merely 20 percent of individuals with drug dependency issues obtained treatment in 2010.

The field of preventative science posits that adverse health consequences, such as those stemming from substance misuse, can be averted by the reduction of risk factors and the augmentation of protective factors. The present paper adopts a broad framework that draws upon research findings put forth by the National Institute of Drug Abuse (NIDA). The framework underscores the significance of directing attention towards modifiable risk factors and bolstering protective factors via preventative programs implemented within the family, school, and community contexts (Chakravarthy et al., 2013).

Moving forward, in terms of the context of the United States, the War on Drugs was first announced by President Nixon in 1973 and later reaffirmed by President Reagan in 1982. President Reagan implemented various strategies to intensify this campaign, such as augmenting the budget allocated to anti-drug enforcement, establishing a federal drug task force, and cultivating a societal environment that stigmatized drug use and individuals involved in drug-related activities. According to the Bureau of Justice

Statistics of the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2008), there was a threefold increase in the number of arrests for drug possession between 1982 and 2007, with figures rising from around 500,000 to 1.5 million. Consequently, drug-related charges currently represent the most prevalent category of arrests in the United States. The prevalence of racial and ethnic disparities in drug-related arrests has witnessed a notable escalation. Specifically, the proportion of black individuals involved in drug-related arrests increased from 22% in 1976 to 40% in 1992, while the corresponding figures for white individuals were 77% and 59%, respectively. It is important to note that during this period, the black population constituted approximately 12% of the total population, whereas the white population accounted for around 82%. Significantly, there was a fall in arrests for all offenses, except for a modest increase in assaults, during the mentioned period. Furthermore, the racial and ethnic disparities in arrests for these other offenses either stayed unchanged or decreased (Cooper, 2015).

The allocation of resources towards police forces and finance experienced a substantial surge to provide extensive assistance for the war on drugs. As an illustration, during the period from 1992 to 2008, there was a twofold increase in state and local expenditures allocated toward police services, rising from \$131 per capita to \$260 per capita. Additionally, federal expenditures also experienced growth during this timeframe. According to Meeks (2006), the allocation of additional financial resources from federal, state, and local authorities towards law enforcement has resulted in a notable augmentation of the number of officers actively engaged in street patrols. The population of sworn officers in the United States experienced a notable growth of 26% during the period spanning from 1992 to 2008. The number of law enforcement personnel conducting patrols within the confines of New York City experienced a notable surge of 47% during the period spanning from 1990 to 1997. The expansion of police authority and the allocation of resources also played a significant role in facilitating the implementation of the War on Drugs. This analysis will primarily examine two specific alterations: the degradation of the Fourth Amendment and the deterioration of the Posse Comitatus Act (Cooper, 2015).

➤ *Local Studies*

The research conducted by Aguisando et al. (2017) aimed to analyze the news reports pertaining to drug warfare, with a focus on examining the language forms and structures employed, as well as identifying the various framing techniques employed within these articles. The study collected a total of thirty (30) articles, with an equal distribution of fifteen (15) items sourced from CNN and fifteen (15) articles sourced from ANC. The researchers discovered that the predominant news reports on the war on drugs in the Philippines, as determined by the lead paragraphs and content, encompass the following themes: reports on the killings of individuals suspected of involvement in drug-related activities, news concerning government officials implicated in illegal drug operations, coverage of drug lords, reports on foreign nationals engaged in illicit drug trade, and news about drug users or dealers who have voluntarily surrendered. The study additionally uncovered that the news reports exhibited linguistic characteristics that could potentially elicit feelings of rage among certain readers. The descriptors employed to characterize the deceased drug suspects, as well as the victims, involved the application of modifiers in conjunction with quantifiers and numerical values. These modifiers were utilized to indicate the number of slain drug suspects, government officials implicated in illicit drug activities, apprehended and deceased drug lords, as well as drug users and dealers who voluntarily surrendered. In contrast, the findings of this study indicate that a significant proportion of the news articles employed thematic framing, as they focused on the underlying issues that contributed to the situation and effectively engaged the public's interest in the current state of society.

Meanwhile, the objective of the study of Guay and Cawi (2021) was to investigate the execution of the war on drugs initiative in the municipality of Alfonso Lista, Ifugao. Their study employed a descriptive qualitative research design to examine the interconnected factors that influence the implementation of the war on drugs program. It also aimed to identify the obstacles faced by those responsible for implementing the program, the strategies used to address these challenges, and recommendations for improving the efficiency of implementation. Thematic analysis was employed to ascertain the topics that emerged from the interview. The primary informants in this study were selected using a purposive sampling technique. They included the barangay chairman, community members, church and educational officers, Philippine National Police (PNP) personnel, and Local Government Units (LGU) officials.

Furthermore, the researchers (Guay and Cawi) aimed to explore the efficacy of implementing a binding foundation program or a localized war on drugs initiative. This investigation sought to determine the extent to which such programs could accurately forecast the level of support for the anti-crime and anti-drug campaign among police officers, local government unit (LGU) officials, and the community residing in the municipality of Alfonso Lista, Ifugao. The research findings about the factors and obstacles faced by police officers, LGU officials, and the community, as well as the strategies employed by them to address the challenges in implementing the war on drugs program, will serve as the foundation for developing a localized war on drugs program (Guay & Cawi, 2021).

On the other hand, Mijares (2020) posited that the War on Drugs initiated by President Duterte in the Philippines, commonly referred to as tokhang (denoting summary killings), has garnered significant criticism from several stakeholders. Civil society organizations, human rights groups, Western democracies, and international entities such as Amnesty International have vehemently condemned the campaign due to its perceived brutality and the perceived lack of accountability for those involved. There has been significant public outcry regarding the indiscriminate homicides of individuals alleged to be involved in drug addiction, primarily affecting males residing in poor metropolitan regions. This study examines the intersection of class and gender within the context

of the drug war, employing a feminist theoretical framework. This study focuses on the experiences of women who have been left behind by the victims of tokhang and explores the subsequent impact of their victimization on their political agency. This study employs the stories of women and examines their importance in challenging the prevailing culture of fear and silence. The significance of these testimonials extends to the cultivation of awareness and the fostering of unity among individuals who have experienced state violence. Additionally, they serve to advocate for collaborative efforts aimed at addressing and combating state violence. The testimonials also shed light on the difficulties that women encounter when they confront state violence, which is carried out by male state agents. This study examines the power imbalances between the state and its victims, focusing on the experiences of women who, in collaboration with civil society organizations, are working towards rebuilding their lives in the aftermath of Duterte's war on drugs.

➤ *Synthesis of the Related Studies*

The literature on drug-related issues spans global perspectives and local contexts, providing a multifaceted understanding of the challenges and strategies involved. Chakravarthy et al. (2013) and the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) highlight the global health concern of substance misuse, emphasizing the need for preventative science and addressing risk factors (Chakravarthy et al., 2013). The United States' War on Drugs, initiated in the 1970s and intensified under President Reagan, is examined in terms of arrests, racial disparities, and resource allocation (Cooper, 2015). This period saw a significant increase in arrests for drug possession, with racial disparities becoming more pronounced. Financial resources allocated to law enforcement substantially increased, leading to a growth in the number of officers and impacting constitutional norms like the Fourth Amendment (Cooper, 2015). Local studies in the Philippines by Aguisando et al. (2017), Guay and Cawi (2021), and Mijares (2020) offer insights into the media framing of drug warfare, the implementation of anti-drug programs at the local level, and the gendered impact of President Duterte's War on Drugs. Aguisando et al. (2017) analyze news reports, highlighting linguistic characteristics that may evoke strong emotions, while Guay and Cawi (2021) investigate the challenges and strategies of implementing a localized war on drugs initiative. Mijares (2020) explores the feminist perspective on the War on Drugs, focusing on the experiences of women affected by tokhang and their role in challenging state violence. These studies collectively present a comprehensive view of the global and local dimensions of drug-related issues, encompassing health, law enforcement, media framing, and societal impacts.

D. *Theoretical Framework*

➤ *Kotter's Change Management Theory*

The 8-Step Change Management Model developed by Kotter (1996) is a systematic approach aimed at assisting leaders in effectively executing organizational transformation initiatives. The model under discussion was formulated by John P. Kotter, an esteemed professor at Harvard Business School, and was expounded upon in his publication titled "Leading Change." This model is the result of an extensive study conducted over a significant period, which revealed a somewhat disheartening statistic indicating that the likelihood of successfully implementing organizational transformation stands at a mere 30%.

The Kotter 8-step approach is widely recognized and favored because it provides a straightforward and comprehensible framework for change managers, regardless of their level of expertise in the discipline. Each stage delineates the specific actions required to maintain the progress of a change project. The concept emphasizes generating a sense of urgency to facilitate the occurrence of a transformative shift. The provided framework guides individuals in navigating the stages of instigating, overseeing, and upholding change, encompassing a total of eight sequential processes. Currently, numerous firms undergoing transition employ the Kotter change management paradigm.

➤ *Prosci ADKAR Change Management Model*

The Prosci ADKAR Model is considered one of the fundamental models inside the Prosci Methodology, alongside the PCT Model. The term "ADKAR" represents an initialism denoting the five essential outcomes that an individual must attain for a change to be effectively implemented: awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement.

The model was established approximately twenty years ago by Jeff Hiatt, the creator of Prosci, after an extensive analysis of the change patterns exhibited by over seven hundred firms. The ADKAR model is being utilized by numerous change leaders across the globe.

This robust paradigm is predicated on the premise that organizational change is contingent upon individual change. While the Prosci 3-Phase Process serves as a framework for implementing organizational change, the ADKAR Model primarily emphasizes individual change by providing guidance to individuals during a specific change initiative and addressing any obstacles or challenges that may arise during the process.

E. Conceptual Framework

Fig 1: Research Paradigm

The IPO Model is a functional framework for conceptualizing ideas that can be used to generate new ones. It provides methods for gaining a deeper understanding of how ideas work and for making the most of their details. IPO is a functional graph that identifies the inputs, outputs, and processing activities that are necessary to change inputs into outputs. IPO is used to represent a process flow. In some cases, the model is set to include any storage that may occur during the process as well as the actual storage. The input, as the initial step phase of this research, represents the drug-related crime rates, the concept of change in administration, a review of related literature, and the theories used for the study. From the figure below, it can be gleaned that the process will start with data collection with the use of a validated researcher-made questionnaire, and then comes the data analysis of the results. This step also includes the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the results for a better understanding of the results. Finally, the output will be a proposed intervention measure.

F. Significance of the Study

This study is very beneficial to the following:

- To the **government agencies, particularly the Philippine National Police.** This study will benefit them because it will provide them with an intervention measure that can help in the reduction of drug-related crime rates within the research locale.
- To the **law enforcement personnel:** This study will be very beneficial to them because it will be a good source of knowledge and awareness on the topic, especially since they are the target population of this study.
- To the **academy:** This study will be beneficial to the academic community because it will add to the growing literature on the topic and enrich the study of this topic.
- To the **Future Researchers:** This study will benefit them because it will give them insights and knowledge about this specific topic should they choose to revisit or pursue it in the future.
- To the **researcher:** This study will be very beneficial to the researcher because it will help the latter's understanding of the said topic.

G. Definition of Terms

- **Community support and trust.** This refers to the trust that the police need for their work to become much more effective.
- **Crime rate.** It refers to the number of crimes that are committed during a period in a particular place.
- **Crime Trend.** This is defined as a significant change in the nature of selected crime types within a defined geographical area and time period.
- **Drug-awareness drive.** It aims to inform people about the risks of drug use and give them practical skills to make decisions that minimize harm.
- **Law enforcement operations.** These are defined as the job duties, responsibilities, and activities that law enforcement agents complete in the field.
- **Motivation for police.** It refers to the encouragement and practice of authenticity and accountability to promote credibility among the police force.

H. Statement of the Problem

This study aims to analyze the effects of the change of administration on the drug-related crime rates of the Gandara Police Community Precinct.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

- What is the perceived level of effectiveness of drug-related operations in administrative transitions in terms of:
 - ✓ Drug-awareness drive;
 - ✓ Drug-law enforcement operations;
 - ✓ Community trust and support; and
 - ✓ Motivation of police
- What are the effects of administrative transitions on the following aspects within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of:
 - ✓ Drug-awareness drive;
 - ✓ Drug-law enforcement operations;
 - ✓ Community trust and support;
 - ✓ Motivation of police;
 - ✓ Crime Trends; and
 - ✓ Crime Patterns?
- Based on the result, what intervention measures can be proposed?

CHAPTER TWO METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The method of investigation utilized both descriptive quantitative and qualitative research approaches. Observing and describing a subject's behavior is the focus of the descriptive technique, a type of research approach used in the scientific community. Research that falls under the category of "descriptive" seeks to describe a population, situation, or event accurately and methodically. The objective of descriptive research is to determine the condition that predominates in a group of variables that have been selected for study. Descriptive research is defined as fact-finding with adequate interpretation and the true meaning of data collected that are reported from the viewpoint of the objective and basic assumptions of the research (McCombes, 2022). Meanwhile, the qualitative research approach is a process of naturalistic inquiry that seeks an in-depth understanding of social phenomena within their natural setting.

This study used a descriptive quantitative study to determine the level of effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions through the use of a researcher-made survey questionnaire. Meanwhile, a qualitative research design was used to determine the effects of administrative transitions on the following aspects within the Gandara Police Community Precinct, using interviews that will be conducted with the officials of the said community precinct.

A. Research Method

The study consists of a set of data or information analyzed, summarized, and interpreted to pursue the specific purpose of conducting the study. Questionnaires will be given personally by the researcher and collected as well. After the collection, the data will be tabulated to create a statistical treatment to be able to present, interpret, and analyze the collected data.

B. Population of the Study

The total number of respondents in the study is 300. The first part of the total number of respondents, or 20 of the 300 total respondents, had the following inclusion criteria: (a) have been working for at least three (3) years for the Gandara Police Community Precinct, and (b) are actively involved in drug-related crimes in the said community. The researcher of this study came up with 20 as the sample size for this group of respondents because it already represents most of the workforce of the said community precinct. Meanwhile, the remaining respondents for this study were community residents that are currently residing within the Gandara. In addition, in choosing the respondents, the researcher of this study utilized the purposive random sampling technique. The researcher came up with the number of respondents from the community population, which is estimated at 1,000, and using Slovin's formula, it yielded a sample size of 285, 285.71, or 286, stating the level of significance at 5%. Furthermore, the researcher utilized purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique. In purposive sampling, the researcher facilitates the collection of qualitative responses, thereby enhancing the depth of understanding and accuracy of study outcomes. The relevance of the results to the research context is ensured by the researcher's collection of information from participants who best align with the research criteria.

C. Locale of the Study

This study was conducted within the area of the municipality of Gandara in Binondo, Manila. Binondo, a prominent district located in the city of Manila, is well recognized as the Chinatown of the metropolis. The influence extends beyond the geographical boundaries of Quiapo, Santa Cruz, San Nicolas, and Tondo. The oldest Chinatown globally was founded in 1594 by the Spanish colonizers as a colony adjacent to Intramuros, although situated on the opposite side of the Pasig River, specifically designated for Catholic Chinese individuals. This strategic placement allowed the colonial authorities to closely monitor the activities of the migrating Chinese population. Before the Spanish colonial era, the region had already established itself as a prominent center for Chinese commerce. Binondo serves as the focal point of commerce and trade in Manila, housing a diverse array of thriving businesses predominantly owned and operated by Filipino-Chinese entrepreneurs.

Fig 2: Map of Gandara in Binondo, Manila

D. Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study was conducted to thoroughly analyze the effects of the change of administration on the drug-related crime rates of the Gandara Police Community Precinct. Due to the limited time, the researcher was expected to employ person-to-person surveys and testing methods to gather and analyze the data. With this kind of methodology, constraints such as the uncooperativeness of respondents and the inaccuracy of responses may be encountered. The data collection will be conducted with respondents who are community residents and police officers designated at the Police Community Precinct of Gandara. The study ran for one year and covered the formulation of the research title up to the eventual defense of the whole study. The researcher also referred to books, periodicals, articles, and electronic publications as research resources. Said secondary data were reflected in the study's review of related literature and studies. Furthermore, any topics that are outside the purview of the above-mentioned topic will not be covered by this study.

E. Data Gathering Tools

The questionnaire was utilized in the data gathering. The questionnaire used was composed of three significant parts. The first part of the questionnaire refers to the demographic profile of the respondents. The second and third parts of the questionnaire will discuss drug-related crimes, as well as their rates and trends, within the jurisdiction of the Gandara Community Precinct.

After creating the questionnaire, it underwent expert validation to test the appropriate usage of words, terms, and definitions in achieving the purpose of the study. The help of two experts was utilized to review the face and content validation of the questionnaire. The chosen experts were from the discipline of criminal justice. Lastly, the researcher improved the instrument based on the experts' suggestions and recommendations.

Following the validation procedure, the researcher distributed the questionnaire to at least 30 respondents in a pilot study to evaluate the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. In addition, the respondents were consulted before the researcher executed the pilot testing. The result of the pilot test was revealed using Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for the Likert-type scales data analysis tool to test the internal consistency of a questionnaire. A high correlation signals a high internal consistency. As a standard procedure, the researcher computed using Cronbach's alpha in Microsoft Excel, where a score of 0.9 or higher is regarded as excellent, 0.8 to 0.7 as good and acceptable, 0.6 to 0.5 as dubious and subpar, and less than 0.5 as unsatisfactory.

F. Data Gathering Procedure

The data were gathered in a series of steps. First permission to survey the chosen companies. The questionnaire was directly tied to the title of the study. In addition to adapting the research questionnaire, the proponent wrote a letter of consent for the study's participants. The questionnaire was tested to establish the instrument's validity and reliability. The data collection began following the validity testing and when the Dean of the Graduate School Department granted the request for data collection. The proponents of this study distributed the research questionnaire to each respondent individually. Finally, after gathering data, the proponent of this study assessed and weighed the findings and started the retrieval, tabulation, processing, analysis, and interpretation of the data with the

assistance of a statistician. Furthermore, the data gathering took the form of questionnaires. The questions were distributed in person, and respondents responded for roughly 10–15 minutes.

G. Treatment of Data

Frequency and percentage were used to answer the demographic profile of the respondents.

A data visualization known as a percentage frequency distribution displays, as its name suggests, the percentage of observations that are associated with each data point or cluster of data points. It is an effective method for conveying the relative frequency of survey responses and other types of data.

Tables, bar graphs, and pie charts are common representations of pie charts, bar graphs, and percentage frequency distributions.

The weighted mean and ranking were computed with an extra weight applied to one or more sample elements. The weighted average of observed data is calculated by multiplying each component by a factor that reflects its importance.

H. Ethical Considerations

Many groups, including the Committee on Publication Ethics, work to promote academic research ethics. These organizations agree that ethics should not be an afterthought or an afterthought in a research endeavor. It is an important aspect of the study that must be prioritized in our efforts in the future.

Research investigations should not collect research respondent data unless it is critical to the analysis technique.

Respondents in this study have the option to accept or decline participation in the study. Anonymity will be widely practiced because it is the quality or state of being unknown to most individuals. The study will have access to identifiable information for any data that will be collected electronically, but it should not be disclosed without the participants' permission. Furthermore, the data gathered and samples should be preserved, and data privacy should be used to protect respondents' anonymity. Finally, respondents should not be exposed to unjustified or unreasonable amounts of risk. As a result, it must be ensured that this study is done with honesty and integrity, that participants' identity and confidentiality are protected, and that any risks to participants are minimized.

I. Dissemination of the Research Outcome

After finishing the research, the researcher aims to present the study and its findings to the members of the academic committee for the thesis defense. It is also the aim of the researchers to consider the comments and ideas of the panel to improve the quality and contents of the study. Furthermore, after conducting the study, the researcher hopes to provide sufficient knowledge on the topic. The researcher also envisions that the findings of this study will be beneficial to the continuous decline of drug-related crimes, not only in Gandara and Binondo but in the rest of the country.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. *Perceived Level of Effectiveness of Drug-Related Operations of Administrative Transitions*

- Drug-awareness drive;
- Drug-law enforcement operations;
- Community trust and support; and
- Motivation of police

The administrative transition in the presidential leadership gives rise to a query on the current status of the drug-related law enforcement operations of the Philippine National Police. A discussion of the results of the query/research investigation follows.

The overall mean of 3.03 indicates that the surveyed community strongly agrees with the perceived level of effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions, specifically in the context of drug awareness drives. This suggests a positive reception of the efforts undertaken during administrative transitions to address the issue of drug abuse through awareness campaigns and other related measures.

Table 1: Perceived Level of Effectiveness of Drug-Related Operations of Administrative Transitions in Terms of Drug Awareness Drive

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The drug awareness campaigns conducted during administrative transitions have been very effective in educating the community about the dangers of drug abuse.	3.22	STRONGLY AGREE
The transition period has shown a positive impact on reducing drug-related incidents due to the implementation of effective administrative measures.	3.14	STRONGLY AGREE
The communication strategies employed during administrative transitions have effectively conveyed the importance of maintaining a drug-free environment.	2.89	AGREE
The coordination and collaboration among administrative entities during transitions have significantly contributed to the success of drug prevention initiatives.	3.01	STRONGLY AGREE
The community's perception of the effectiveness of drug-related operations has improved during administrative transitions, reflecting the success of awareness programs.	2.88	AGREE
OVERALL MEAN	3.03	STRONGLY AGREE

The top two highest weighted means, 3.22 and 3.14, highlight the significant impact of drug awareness campaigns and effective administrative measures during transitions. These results indicate that the community strongly believes that these initiatives have been instrumental in educating them about the dangers of drug abuse and have contributed positively to reducing drug-related incidents. The high ratings suggest that such activities are viewed as crucial in fostering a drug-free environment.

Conversely, the two lowest weighted means, 2.89 and 2.88, pertain to the effectiveness of communication strategies and the community's perception of the overall success of drug prevention initiatives during administrative transitions. While these scores still indicate that the surveyed community agrees, there may be room for improvement in communication strategies to enhance their impact, and efforts may be needed to further align community perceptions with the success of drug prevention initiatives.

In the analysis of the overall result, the community's positive perception, with an overall mean of 3.03, underscores the importance of incorporating drug awareness campaigns and effective administrative measures during transitions. The surveyed community's strong agreement reflects successful collaboration among administrative entities and suggests a positive trend toward improving the community's awareness and response to drug-related issues. Continuous efforts in refining communication strategies and addressing any perceived gaps could further enhance the overall impact of these operations in promoting a drug-free environment.

The overall mean perceived level of effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions is noteworthy, standing at 3.12. This indicates a generally positive perception among the public regarding the impact of law enforcement efforts in curbing illegal drug activities during administrative transitions. The community strongly agrees with the operation of administrative transitions.

Table 2: Perceived Level of Effectiveness of Drug-Related Operations of Administrative Transitions in terms of Drug Law Enforcement Operations

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The law enforcement efforts implemented during administrative transitions have been very effective in curbing illegal drug activities.	2.97	AGREE
The administrative transitions have demonstrated a noticeable improvement in the enforcement of drug-related laws, leading to a reduction in drug-related crimes.	3.17	STRONGLY AGREE
The coordination between law enforcement agencies during administrative transitions has played a significant role in enhancing the overall effectiveness of drug control operations.	2.85	AGREE
The public's perception of the effectiveness of drug law enforcement operations has positively changed during administrative transitions.	3.33	STRONGLY AGREE
The implementation of stricter measures and penalties for drug-related offenses during administrative transitions has contributed to a more effective deterrence against drug-related crimes.	3.28	STRONGLY AGREE
OVERALL MEAN	3.12	STRONGLY AGREE

Among the top two highest weighted means, the responses highlight the effectiveness of administrative transitions in improving the enforcement of drug-related laws, resulting in a reduction in drug-related crimes. With a mean of 3.17, the surveyed community strongly agrees with the reduction in drug-related crimes. This suggests that the changes implemented during transitions are making a noticeable positive impact on the control and prevention of drug-related offenses.

Conversely, the two lowest-weighted means indicate areas for potential improvement. The mean of 2.85 for the coordination between law enforcement agencies during transitions suggests that there might be room for enhancing collaboration and communication between agencies to further improve the overall effectiveness of drug control operations. Additionally, despite the positive shift in perception, the mean of 2.97 for the general effectiveness of law enforcement efforts during transitions indicates that there may still be a segment of the public that sees room for improvement.

In the analysis of the overall result, the positive change in the public's perception of the effectiveness of drug law enforcement operations during administrative transitions is evident. This suggests that the implementation of stricter measures and penalties, combined with improved enforcement and collaboration between agencies, has contributed to a more effective deterrence against drug-related crimes. The overall mean of 3.12 reinforces the notion that administrative transitions play a crucial role in bolstering the perceived effectiveness of drug control operations, reflecting a positive outlook on the impact of these transitional periods.

Table 3: Perceived Level of Effectiveness of Drug-Related Operations of Administrative Transitions in Terms of Community Trust and Support

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The communication and transparency regarding drug-related operations during administrative transitions have been very effective in gaining the trust of the community.	2.81	AGREE
The community feels confident in the ability of administrative transitions to address and respond to drug-related issues.	2.99	STRONGLY AGREE
The engagement of the community in decision-making processes related to drug prevention initiatives during administrative transitions has been perceived as very effective.	3.13	STRONGLY AGREE
The community perceives that their concerns and feedback regarding drug-related operations are taken into account during administrative transitions.	2.78	AGREE
The support and cooperation from the community have increased as a result of effective communication and collaboration during administrative transitions to combat drug-related challenges.	3.21	STRONGLY AGREE
OVERALL MEAN	2.98	AGREE

The overall mean of 2.98 indicates that the perceived level of effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions, in terms of community trust and support, is generally considered effective. This suggests that the surveyed community agrees that the efforts made in communication, transparency, and community engagement have contributed positively to building

trust and support within the community during these transitions.

The two highest weighted means, 3.13 and 3.21, highlight specific areas where the community strongly agrees that there is exceptional effectiveness. The engagement of the community in decision-making processes related to drug prevention initiatives (3.13) and the increased support and cooperation from the community (3.21) demonstrate that involving the community in these initiatives during administrative transitions has been particularly successful. These findings emphasize the importance of fostering collaboration and participation in shaping and implementing strategies to address drug-related challenges.

On the other hand, the two lowest weighted means, 2.78 and 2.81, indicate areas that may require additional attention. The perception that concerns and feedback regarding drug-related operations are taken into account (2.78) and the overall mean (2.81) show that while the surveyed community agrees that the operations are effective, there is room for improvement in ensuring that community input is consistently considered during administrative transitions. Addressing these areas can further enhance the overall effectiveness of drug-related operations.

In analysis of the overall result, the data suggests that open communication, transparency, and community engagement play crucial roles in establishing trust and garnering support during administrative transitions related to drug operations. As the overall mean indicates that the surveyed community agrees that there is trust and confidence, it implies a positive perception of the efforts made, but continuous efforts to address concerns and improve community involvement can contribute to further strengthening the bond between the community and administrative transitions in combating drug-related challenges.

Table 4: Perceived Level of Effectiveness of Drug-Related Operations of Administrative Transitions in Terms of Motivation of Police

Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
The implementation of new strategies and resources during administrative transitions has been very effective in motivating police officers to address drug-related issues proactively.	3.33	STRONGLY AGREE
The training and support provided to law enforcement personnel during administrative transitions have positively impacted their motivation to combat drug-related crimes.	3.46	STRONGLY AGREE
Police officers are motivated by the changes in policies and procedures during administrative transitions aimed at enhancing their effectiveness in dealing with drug-related challenges.	3.12	STRONGLY AGREE
The recognition and acknowledgment of the efforts of police officers involved in drug-related operations during administrative transitions have effectively boosted their motivation.	3.10	STRONGLY AGREE
The sense of purpose and clear objectives communicated to the police force during administrative transitions has been very effective in motivating them to actively contribute to drug prevention initiatives.	2.98	AGREE
OVERALL MEAN	3.20	STRONGLY AGREE

The overall mean of 3.20 suggests a generally positive perception of the effectiveness of administrative transitions in motivating police officers to address drug-related issues. This indicates that, on average, the implementation of new strategies and resources, training and support, changes in policies and procedures, recognition of efforts, and communication of clear objectives have collectively contributed to a high level of motivation among police officers.

Examining the top two highest weighted means, which are 3.46 and 3.33, reveals that the training and support provided to law enforcement personnel and the implementation of new strategies and resources have been particularly impactful in boosting motivation. This underscores the importance of investing in the professional development and resources of police officers during administrative transitions, as it directly influences their commitment to combating drug-related crimes.

On the other hand, the two lowest weighted means, 2.98 and 3.10, focus on the sense of purpose and clear objectives communicated during administrative transitions and the recognition of officers' efforts. While still considered effective, these areas might benefit from further attention and improvement to ensure a more comprehensive and uniform impact on officers' motivation.

In the overall analysis, the positive perception of administrative transitions on the perceived level of effectiveness in motivating police officers to address drug-related issues highlights the importance of a holistic approach, encompassing training, resources, policy changes, recognition, and effective communication of objectives during these transitional phases. This result provides valuable insights

for law enforcement agencies looking to enhance officer motivation and, consequently, the success of drug-related operations.

B. Effects of Administrative Transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct

Statement of the problem 2: What are the effects of administrative transitions on the following aspects within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of:

- Drug-awareness drive;
- Drug-law enforcement operations;
- Community trust and support;
- Motivation of police;
- Crime trends; and
- Crime Patterns

➤ *Observed Number of Drug-awareness Drives Launched in Gandara and the Response of the Community in terms of the said Drug-awareness Drives*

“The community response in terms of the drug awareness drives was positive, with increased attendance and engagement.” (Participant 1)

“The community response was enthusiastic, with a surge in participation and interest.” (Participant 2)

The qualitative data provided by participants from the Gandara Police Community Precinct highlights a notable shift in the community's response to drug awareness drives following administrative transitions. Participant 1's observation underscores a positive trend, noting increased attendance and engagement during these initiatives. This indicates a heightened interest and involvement from the community, suggesting that efforts to raise awareness about drug abuse are being well-received.

Participant 2's feedback further reinforces this positive momentum, emphasizing an enthusiastic community response characterized by a surge in participation and interest. This enthusiastic engagement signifies a significant departure from previous levels of involvement, reflecting a growing awareness and commitment to addressing drug-related issues within the community.

These responses collectively suggest that the administrative transitions have brought about tangible improvements in the effectiveness of drug-awareness initiatives in Gandara. The increased community participation and enthusiasm indicate a strengthening of community partnerships and a more proactive approach to combating drug abuse. This shift towards greater community involvement bodes well for the sustainability and impact of ongoing efforts to promote drug awareness and prevention in the area.

➤ *Effects of Administrative Transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of Drug Law Enforcement Operations*

“There's a noticeable shift in the strategy of drug-law enforcement operations. The new administration has placed a strong emphasis on intelligence-led operations and collaboration with other law enforcement agencies. We're leveraging advanced technology to enhance surveillance and tracking capabilities, making our operations more targeted and effective.” (Participant 1)

“There's a noticeable shift towards a more coordinated and intelligence-driven approach in drug-law enforcement operations.” (Participant 2)

“The new administration is encouraging joint operations with other law enforcement agencies, and we're leveraging advanced technology for better surveillance and tracking. This has enhanced the overall effectiveness of our operations.” (Participant 3)

The qualitative data from participants within the Gandara Police Community Precinct highlights a discernible transformation in the approach to drug law enforcement operations following administrative transitions. A common theme across the responses is the explicit shift towards an intelligence-led strategy, indicative of a departure from traditional methods. Participant 1 notes a significant emphasis on collaboration with other law enforcement agencies and the utilization of advanced technology for enhanced surveillance and tracking. This shift aligns with contemporary policing trends that prioritize targeted and efficient operations based on actionable intelligence.

Moreover, Participant 2 emphasizes the evolution towards a more coordinated and intelligence-driven approach, echoing the sentiments expressed by Participant 1. The repetition of phrases such as "intelligence-led operations" and "collaboration with other law enforcement agencies" suggests a deliberate and systematic change in the overall approach to drug law enforcement. Additionally, Participant 3 reiterates the positive impact of joint operations and the integration of advanced technology in improving the overall

effectiveness of operations. The consensus among participants points towards a strategic realignment in the Gandara Police Community Precinct, underscoring a commitment to modernize and optimize drug law enforcement through intelligence-driven collaboration and technological advancements.

➤ *Effects of Administrative Transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in Terms of Community Trust and Support*
 “The community's trust and support have improved significantly during the transition. The leadership has emphasized transparency and accountability, holding regular meetings with community members and addressing their concerns. This has resulted in a stronger bond between the police and the community.” (Participant 1)

“Trust and support from the community have improved. The new leadership has encouraged more community involvement in decision-making processes and has actively sought feedback.” (Participant 2)

“The new leadership has encouraged more community involvement in decision-making processes and has actively sought feedback. This has fostered a stronger relationship between the police and the community, resulting in increased trust and support.” (Participant 3)

It can be noted that the result suggests that the effects of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct have been overwhelmingly positive in terms of community trust and support. The recurring theme across the participants' responses is the improvement in trust and support, highlighting a significant shift in the relationship between the police and the community. The emphasis on transparency and accountability by the new leadership is a key factor contributing to this positive change. Regular meetings with community members and addressing their concerns have played a pivotal role in building a stronger bond between the police and the community. This indicates that open communication and a willingness to address community needs are crucial elements in fostering trust.

Furthermore, the new leadership's proactive approach towards community involvement in decision-making processes and actively seeking feedback has been a driving force behind the increased trust and support. Participant 3 specifically notes that this approach has resulted in a stronger relationship between the police and the community. The data suggests that empowering the community by involving them in decision-making not only enhances a sense of ownership but also builds mutual understanding and cooperation. Overall, the qualitative data indicates that the administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct have positively impacted community trust and support through transparent communication, accountability, and active community involvement.

➤ *Effects of Administrative Transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of Internal Communication Within the Police Precinct, in Place to Keep the Police Officers Motivated to do their Jobs*
 “Morale and motivation within the police force have seen a positive boost during the transition. The leadership has implemented recognition programs, provided additional training opportunities, and improved working conditions. These initiatives have contributed to a more motivated and dedicated police force.” (Participant 1)

“There's a positive shift in the motivation of the police force. The new leadership has implemented initiatives to recognize and reward outstanding performance. This, along with improved training opportunities, has created a more motivated and dedicated police force committed to serving the community.” (Participant 2)

“The new administration has implemented recognition programs and provided additional training opportunities. This has created a more motivated and dedicated police force, which is essential for effective community policing.” (Participant 3)

The qualitative data suggests a consistent and positive impact of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct on the motivation of the police force. Participants consistently highlight the implementation of recognition programs and the provision of additional training opportunities as key factors contributing to the observed increase in morale and dedication among the police officers. The emphasis on acknowledging outstanding performance through recognition initiatives appears to be a crucial aspect of the positive shift in motivation. This suggests that the new leadership has successfully prioritized creating a supportive and rewarding work environment, fostering a sense of appreciation among the police force.

Moreover, the data emphasizes the importance of improved working conditions and training opportunities in enhancing motivation. The mention of a more motivated and dedicated police force being essential for effective community policing suggests that these changes are not only benefiting the individual officers but also contributing to the overall effectiveness of law enforcement efforts within the community. The consistent positive feedback from multiple participants strengthens the credibility of the findings, highlighting a holistic improvement in the motivation and dedication of the police force as a result of the administrative transitions.

➤ *Effects of Administrative Transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of Crime Trends and Patterns*

“Analyzing crime patterns has become more data-driven and focused. The new leadership has introduced a proactive approach, utilizing technology to identify emerging crime patterns. This allows for a quicker response and better resource allocation to address specific crime patterns within the community.” (Participant 1)

“There's been a noticeable reduction in drug-related crimes. The targeted efforts in drug law enforcement, coupled with community engagement, have contributed to this positive trend. While challenges persist, the overall impact on crime trends is promising.” (Participant 2)

“In terms of crime trends, there's been a positive impact on drug-related offenses. The focused efforts in drug law enforcement and community engagement have contributed to a decrease in such crimes. While challenges remain, the overall trend is promising.” (Participant 3)

The qualitative data provides insights into the effects of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct, specifically focusing on crime trends and patterns. According to Participant 1, the new leadership has ushered in a more data-driven and proactive approach to crime analysis. The introduction of technology for identifying emerging crime patterns has enabled quicker responses and more efficient resource allocation to address specific criminal activities within the community. This shift towards a proactive strategy suggests a commitment to staying ahead of criminal trends, potentially leading to a more effective and targeted law enforcement response.

Participants 2 and 3 both highlight a noticeable reduction in drug-related crimes as a positive outcome of the administrative transitions. Concerted efforts in drug law enforcement, combined with community engagement initiatives, have contributed to this decline. The emphasis on both law enforcement and community involvement suggests a holistic approach to tackling drug-related offenses. Despite acknowledging persistent challenges, the participants expressed optimism about the overall impact on crime trends. This positive outlook implies that the administrative transitions have had a promising influence on the precinct's ability to address and mitigate specific criminal activities, particularly in the realm of drug-related offenses.

C. Intervention Measures that can be Imposed to Enforce and Improve Policing against Drug-Related Crimes in the Transition of Administration

Based on the findings, the researcher proposes the intervention measures, which will be elaborated in the recommendation:

- An intensive echoing of the importance of community participation in the fight against drug-related crimes.
- Reinforcement of the PNP's role in crime prevention
- PNP Commendations for accomplishments and 8-hour duty to boost the morale of the personnel.

Change the 12-hour duty to an 8-hour duty. It is human nature that when a person is happy at home, the same is their disposition at work. This bold move to lower the number of hours will give PNP personnel more time with their families. Reinforcing and emphasizing the government's drive to remind its citizens of the importance of family quality time.

➤ *Revisiting the Commendations and Awards System. This measure will be further discussed in the recommendation.*

Lastly, there is no significant effect of the transition of administrations. During the transition, the fight against drug-related crimes had been efficient, and there was no increase during the transition period.

CHAPTER FOUR

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. *Summary of Findings*

The following are the findings of the study:

The perceived level of effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions in terms of **drug awareness drive**, the overall assessment of the respondents was strongly agreeable, with an overall mean of 3.03. The drug awareness campaigns obtained the highest mean score of 3.22, and the community's perception of the effectiveness of drug-related operations had the lowest mean score of 2.88. On **drug-law enforcement operations**, the overall assessment of the respondents was strongly agreeable, with an overall mean of 3.12. The public's perception of the effectiveness of drug law enforcement operations obtained the highest mean score of 3.33, and the coordination between law enforcement agencies during administrative transitions has the lowest mean score of 2.85. On **Community trust and support**, the overall assessment of the respondents was AGREE with an overall mean of 2.98. The support and cooperation from the community have increased as a result of effective communication and collaboration, garnering the highest mean score of 3.21, and the community perception that their concerns and feedback regarding drug-related operations are taken into account scored the lowest of 2.78. On **Motivation of police**, the overall assessment of the respondents was strongly agreeable, with an overall mean of 3.20. The training and support provided to law enforcement personnel during administrative transitions have positively impacted their motivation to combat drug-related crimes, with the highest mean of 3.46. The sense of purpose and clear objectives communicated to the police force scored the lowest mean score of 2.98.

The effects of administrative transitions on the following aspects within the Gandara Police Community Precinct in terms of **Drug-awareness drive**, the qualitative data provided by participants from the Gandara Police Community Precinct highlights a notable shift in the community's response to drug-awareness drives following administrative transitions. On **Drug-law enforcement operations**, the qualitative data from participants within the Gandara Police Community Precinct highlights a discernible transformation in the approach to drug-law enforcement operations following administrative transitions. On **Community trust and support**, the result suggests that the effects of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct have been overwhelmingly positive in terms of community trust and support.

On **Motivation of police**, the qualitative data suggests a consistent and positive impact of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct on the motivation of the police force. On **Crime trends and patterns**, the qualitative data provides insights into the effects of administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct, specifically focusing on crime trends and patterns.

Based on the findings, the researcher proposes the following intervention measures: An intensive echoing of the importance of community participation in the fight against drug-related crimes; Reinforcement of the PNP's role in crime prevention; PNP Commendations for accomplishments and 8-hour duty to boost the morale of the personnel (Change the 12-hour duty to an 8-hour duty. It is human nature that when a person is happy at home, the same is their disposition at work. This bold move to lower the number of hours will give PNP personnel more time with their families. Reinforcing and emphasizing the government's drive to remind its citizens of the importance of family quality time; Revisiting the Commendations and Awards System. This measure will be further discussed in the recommendation).

Lastly, there is no significant effect of the transition of administrations. During the transition, the fight against drug-related crimes was efficient, and there was no increase during the transition period.

B. *Conclusions*

In conclusion, the results and discussions regarding the perceived effectiveness of drug-related operations during administrative transitions within the Gandara Police Community Precinct demonstrate a generally positive impact on various aspects of law enforcement and community engagement. The findings reveal that drug awareness drives have been highly effective, with increased community participation and engagement, as Participants 1 and 2 noted. This positive response underscores the success of efforts to raise awareness about drug abuse and foster community involvement in addressing this issue.

Moreover, the data indicates significant improvements in drug law enforcement operations, as highlighted by the shift towards intelligence-led strategies and enhanced collaboration between law enforcement agencies. This approach, emphasized by all participants, has led to a notable reduction in drug-related crimes and a more targeted response to emerging crime patterns.

Furthermore, administrative transitions have positively impacted community trust and support, with enhanced transparency, accountability, and community engagement contributing to stronger police-community relations. Additionally, the motivation of police officers has seen a positive boost, attributed to recognition programs, improved training opportunities, and supportive leadership initiatives.

The findings also suggest promising trends in crime reduction, particularly in drug-related offenses, indicating the effectiveness of coordinated law enforcement efforts and community engagement initiatives. Despite persistent challenges, the overall impact of administrative transitions on crime trends within the precinct appears to be positive and promising.

Overall, the researcher agrees with Tsai et al. (2019) that the primary objective for law enforcement agencies is to formulate effective tactics to address this matter.

C. Recommendations

Based on these results and conclusions, it is recommended that the Gandara Police Community Precinct continues to prioritize drug awareness campaigns, community engagement, intelligence-led law enforcement strategies, and initiatives to boost police morale. Additionally, efforts should be made to address any identified areas for improvement, such as enhancing communication strategies and ensuring consistent community involvement in decision-making processes. Overall, maintaining a proactive and collaborative approach will be essential for sustaining the positive outcomes observed during administrative transitions and effectively addressing drug-related challenges within the community.

➤ *The Following Intervention Measures are Recommended:*

Based on these results and conclusions, it is recommended that the Gandara Police Community Precinct prioritize drug awareness campaigns, community engagement, intelligence-led law enforcement strategies, and initiatives to boost police morale. Additionally, efforts should be made to address any identified areas for improvement, such as enhancing communication strategies and ensuring consistent community involvement in decision-making processes. Maintaining a proactive and collaborative approach will be essential for sustaining the positive outcomes observed during administrative transitions and effectively addressing drug-related challenges within the community.

➤ *The Following Intervention Measures are Recommended:*

- *An Intensive Echoing of the Importance of Community Participation in the Fight Against Drug-Related Crimes to Prioritize Drug Awareness Campaigns and Enhanced Community Engagement*

In coordination with the Manila Police District and following one of the PNP’s vital operational plans for community relations, the Gandara Community Precinct should intensify barangay participation by conducting simple programs and seminars for the community to communicate the significance of civilian participation in the fight against drug-related crimes. This is in agreement with Hughes et al. (2017), who argue that law enforcement agencies should implement a community-based approach to uncover the underlying perceptions of criminal conduct and mitigate the recurrence of drug-related offenses. As we align with Iglesias, in 2023, clearer policy mechanisms and processes for building a more drug-resilient individual, family, and community sector should be formed.

Below is a suggested continuous quarterly timeline for how to implement this program. A year-end report will be required after four quarters, for as long as this program is needed. Modifications can be made as the need arises or ceases.

Table 4.1: Implementing Community Participation

Timeline	Program	Stakeholders	Objectives
1 st Quarter	Daily or Weekly visitation with the barangays and know the particular needs of each.	The barangays within the territory of Gandara PCP	Establish rapport, build trust, and good communication with the barangays in Gandara PCP.
2 nd Quarter	Conduct of Information Drive to the community through the barangay	The barangays within Gandara PCP and their constituents	To communicate the significance of civilian participation in the fight against drug-related crimes.
3 rd Quarter	Continuous visitation to the barangays and its vicinities	The barangays within Gandara PCP and their constituents	While avoiding too much familiarity, by this time, trust between the barangays and the PNP personnel at Gandara PCP should have been established
4 th Quarter	Echoing of the Significance of	The barangays within Gandara	To ensure that there is continuity with

	Community Participation through information drives	PCP and their constituents	the information drives of Gandara PCP
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• *Reinforcement of the PNP’s Role in Crime Prevention to Support Intelligence-Led Law Enforcement Strategies*

When policing is effective, a decline in crime rates is imminent. According to a recent survey by Reddit, Manila is the top city in Southeast Asia with the highest crime rate. Since Gandara PCP is under Meisic Police Station, within the Manila Police District, it is timely to reinforce within the PCP the most important role of the organization, which is crime prevention. Through continuous and enhanced intelligence-led law enforcement strategies, it is the goal of the suggested program to improve police omnipresence and deter the commission of crimes, which will ultimately lead to a significant decrease in the crime rate.

Below is a recommended program with a one-year timeline to implement and continue as necessary or if the program gives positive results. A year-end report will be required after four quarters, for as long as this program is needed. Modifications can be made as the need arises or ceases.

Table 4.2: Necessary to Community Participation

Timeline	Program	Stakeholders	Objectives
1 st Quarter	Technical Working Group (TWG) for the Assessment of Current and Existing Operational Plans of Gandara PCP (Part 1)	Personnel of Gandara PCP	Creation of the TWG to discuss the existing operational plans of the PCP and create a comprehensive assessment of the operational plans and its effectiveness
2 nd Quarter	Technical Working Group (TWG) for the Assessment of Current and Existing Operational Plans of Gandara PCP (Part 2)	Personnel of Gandara PCP	With the current operational plans that the PCP is implementing, those operational plans e suggested to be implemented continuously. And for operational plans that rendered satisfactory but not necessarily effective results, recommend improvements and/or modifications to ensure its effectiveness, enhance omnipresence, and ultimately decrease the commission of crimes
3 rd Quarter	Crime Prevention Information Drive	Personnel of Gandara PCP	Dissemination of the Station units and start implementation
4 th Quarter	Continuous Implementation and Submission of Assessment Report	Personnel of Gandara PCP	Continuous implementation. After every 6-months from implementation, a semestral report should be submitted for proper assessment

• *PNP Commendations for Accomplishments and 8-Hour Duty to Boost the Morale of the Personnel*

The research coincides with Gupta (2002), when he mentioned that the police organization is still human-oriented and that PNP personnel should be kept motivated. The human factor is the unique element of the law enforcement organization, especially those on beat patrol who are the first to interact with the community.

The current Chief PNP, General Rommel Francisco Marbil, also suggests the lessening of the hours of duty from 12 hours to 8 hours for the personnel to spend more time with their family (Franche-Borja, 2024), in connection with Presidential Proclamation No. 326 in January 2012, in conjunction with the annual celebration of Family Week (DSWD, 2021).

Putting emphasis on the foregoing, the following measures will boost the personnel morale:

- ✓ Change the 12-hour duty to an 8-hour duty. It is human nature that when a person is happy at home, the same is their disposition at work. This bold move to lower the number of hours will give PNP personnel more time with their families. Reinforcing and emphasizing the government’s drive to remind its citizens of the importance of family quality time.
- ✓ The following recommended program is a one-year timeline that is suggested to be continuous to have a better commendation and award system. It is also recommended that this program be continuous.

Table 4.3: Continuous Plan on Community Participation

Timeline	Program	Stakeholders	Objectives
1 st Quarter	Revisiting the Guidelines of Commendations and Awards System	The unit in charge of the commendations and awards within Gandara PCP	To revisit the guidelines in the Commendations and Awards system to submit proper recommendations and/or modifications if needed.
2 nd Quarter	Recommendations for the Commendation and Awards System	The unit in charge of the commendations and awards within Gandara PCP	honest Commendation and Award System. For example, for every arrest, especially those offenders belonging to the Most Wanted List, the PNP personnel who were involved in the arrest should be commended, if not rewarded. To eliminate doubts in the integrity of the commendation system, erasing the thought that only those who are close to superiors receive awards and/or commendations
3 rd Quarter	Implementation	Personnel of Gandara PCP	Implementation of the revisited awards system in accordance with existing rules, laws, and regulations.
4 th Quarter	Continuous Implementation and Submission of Assessment Report	Personnel of Gandara PCP	Continuous implementation. A year-end report will be submitted to evaluate the awards and commendations system and the unit in charge to evaluate the effectiveness of the program.

On a final note, it is further recommended that the study be done with a longer timeline. The results showed that the transition of administration did not significantly affect drug-related crime rates. However, based on personal experience, after the transitioning period, or after more than a year of the current administration, there is a significant increase in drug-related crime apprehension. Crimes are more prevalent after the transition period; hence, a longer period for further study is most recommended to support this claim.

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